

MOLECULAR PATTERNS OF RESISTANCE IN *KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIAE*: A CONTINUOUS POTENTIAL THREAT WORLDWIDE

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Abstract

Hypervirulent and Carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* has become a global threat due to its versatile genome which varies geographically. This pathogen is notorious for causing a variety of nosocomial infections especially in immuno-compromised individuals. It harbours various virulence factors such as capsule, enzymes, pili, fimbriae, plasmids, siderophores all of which are encoded by gene or genes clusters present on either chromosome or plasmids that make this pathogen hypervirulent and resistant to multiple drugs, by capturing exogenous genes from within the same species or between different species. Capsular polysaccharide possesses more than 100 antigens which should be targeted by forming vaccine. As geographical distribution of plasmid encoding genes and non plasmid encoded virulent genes is different, whole genome sequencing of isolated *K. pneumoniae* should be done at large scale worldwide in order to design a new and complex vaccine as well as specimen specific antibiotics for this pathogen, to be given worldwide. In addition, designing of siderophore receptors inhibitors hence disrupting organism's metabolism will also be a key threat for organism's survival. This review will discuss molecular patterns that are key players of antimicrobial resistance in *K. pneumoniae* and provide suggestions regarding permanent eradication of this global pathogen.

INTRODUCTION

Klebsiella pneumoniae, first isolated by Friedlander in 1882 from the lungs of patients suffering from pneumonia, is a gram-negative bacterium that is universally distributed such as in plants, animals as well as humans (R Podschun et al., 1998). It belongs to a bacterial family termed Enterobacteriaceae, with a potent and main virulent factor known as capsule, made up of polysaccharide, which aids in its survival from immune cells (C.-R. Lee et al., 2017). Being an opportunistic pathogen e.g. in immuno-compromised patients (Martin & Bachman, 2018) and are routinely treated by Beta-Lactams (Mandell, 2005), mainly causes hospital-acquired

infections which include Pneumonia, Meningitis, liver abscess, urinary tract infection (UTI), wound infection, bacteremia, and sepsis (Martin & Bachman, 2018; Navon-Venezia, Kondratyeva, & Carattoli, 2017). There is a 50% mortality rate with bacteremia caused by carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Opoku-Temeng, Kobayashi, & DeLeo, 2019). In addition, hypervirulent strains affect healthy people only (Hentzien et al., 2017) due to the hypermucous nature of the organism (Fang, Chuang, Shun, Chang, & Wang, 2004). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is a virulent pathogen that is resistant to a broad range of antibiotics (Humphries et al., 2010).

Antimicrobial resistance is a global issue that is accountable for killing a minimum of 1.27 million people worldwide which ended in deaths of almost 5 million people (Control & Prevention, 2019). The antimicrobial resistance is being increased by their improper usage, and diminished availability of new remedies (Organization, 2014) is missing. Numerous factors are accountable for inducing antimicrobial resistance in pathogens including human and animal waste, manufacturing waste, and excretion of large doses of antimicrobials taken by humans or animals as therapeutics or prevention and lack of awareness of usage of antibiotics for humans themselves as well as for animals (Rogers Van Katwyk et al., 2019). The World Health Organization has declared antimicrobial resistance as a global threat that needs to be resolved as soon as possible and on urgent basis (Tamhankar & Stålsby Lundborg, 2019).

Certain virulence genes are involved in forming virulence factors that aid in pathogenesis and culminate in development of a morbidity (Aljanaby & Alhasani, 2016). As per new criteria, there are two pathotypes of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* – that is the classical type that is involved in inducing nosocomial pneumonia with its limited virulence capacity and can exchange mobile genetic elements such as plasmids that result in the production of multi-drug resistant (MDR) strains. On the other hand, hypervirulent *klebsiella pneumoniae* (hpkp) is a hazardous strain carrying plasmids with genes for making it hypervirulent, causing infections in communities (Russo et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2021). The integrative conjugal elements along with plasmids are accountable for inducing virulence in *klebsiella pneumoniae* strains (Russo & Marr, 2019; G. Wang, Zhao, Chao, Xie, & Wang, 2020). There are seven subtypes of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* species on the basis of genomic phylogenetic structure ranging from kp1-kp7. This is actually capsular based typing that can result from gene sequencing such as *wzi* or by serotyping (Gonzalez-Ferrer et al., 2021).

Based on the accessory genome, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* has been divided into opportunistic, hypervirulent multidrug-resistant strains and is an

important tool to distinguish *Klebsiella* species named *Klebsiella variicola* and *Klebsiella quasi pneumoniae*. It is the accessory genome, that determines whether the colonizer will remain asymptomatic or cause disease (Martin & Bachman, 2018). This pathogen has plasmids containing accessory genome and chromosomal gene loci. In addition, carbapenemases and molecular patterns help to verify clinically misinterpreted *klebsiella pneumoniae* strains that may be other species of *klebsiella* (Martin & Bachman, 2018). The accessory genome is the leading cause of antimicrobial resistance making available antibiotics ineffective (Martin & Bachman, 2018). Based on multidrug resistance *klebsiella pneumoniae* has two types such as hvKp and cKp with cKp among the most virulent and emerging one (Alharbi et al., 2023), Antimicrobial resistance is an eternal phenomenon worldwide that can surpass death rate of about 10 million by 2050 (O'Neill, 2019). There is a dire need to diagnose and manage these strains especially hvKp for which string test has become insufficient (Alharbi et al., 2023). In addition other virulence factors such as capsule fimbriae, lipopolysaccharides (LPS) and siderophores (S. Ali, Alam, Hasan, & Hassan, 2022; A. H. Lee et al., 2021) also play part in evolving hypervirulent *klebsiella pneumoniae* strains. A study carried out in 2024 have found out some genes including *acrR*, *ompK35* and *hha* genes that are accountable for resistance (Heng et al., 2024).

This review will focus on molecular patterns such as mobile genetic elements, plasmids along with their types and drug resistance enzymes as well as other virulence factors including capsule, LPS, and siderophores used by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* along with possible future suggestions to control the spread of infections due to this multidrug-resistant bug worldwide.

- **1-*Klebsiella Pneumoniae* a universally threatening bug**

Klebsiella pneumoniae is an opportunistic pathogen, primarily involved in developing nosocomial infections in United states (Magill et al., 2014) causing ventilator-associated pneumonia in intensive care units (Kalanuria, Zai, & Mirski,

2014; Selina et al., 2009). The mortality rate due to bacteremia caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is estimated as 1.3 per 100,000 people (Meatherall, Gregson, Ross, Pitout, & Laupland, 2009). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* affects various sites of the body with urinary tract is the commonest one (Rainer Podschun & Ullmann, 1998). Carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CR-KP) accounts for almost 30% of clinically isolated strains which is challenging for clinicians (Effah, Sun, Liu, & Wu, 2020). Various mechanisms are responsible for the production of CR-KP such as the production of Carbapenemase such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Carbapenemase, New Delhi metallo-beta-lactamases, imipenemases (Lai & Yu, 2021), deprivation or reduced expression of membrane proteins or excessive expression of beta-lactamases (Lan, Jiang, Zhou, & Yu, 2021). Factors such as diabetes mellitus (Chung, 2016) and urinary catheters also favour *klebsiella pneumoniae* infection by forming biofilms (Schroll, Barken, Krogfelt, & Struve, 2010). About 13% of wound site infections are the result of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Magill et al., 2014).

- **1.1: The Accessory Genome**

The accessory genome is a set of genes that differs between bacterial isolates while the core genome has genes that are conserved between bacterial species. About 95% of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates have a core genome containing almost 2000 genes (Holt et al., 2015). The accessory genes harbor chromosome and plasmids encoding antimicrobial-resistant enzymes (Bi et al., 2015). The accessory genes which are mobile genetic elements, can be exchanged between bacterial species via horizontal gene transfer, thus helping bacteria to adapt at various sites as an infective agent or a colonizer (J. Zhang et al., 2011). While virulent strains possess certain virulent factor encoding genes and operons that encode

yersiniabactin, which is a potent virulent factor (Fodah et al., 2014; Holt et al., 2015). Accessory genome elements can be recognized using silico methods (R. Zhang, Ou, Gao, & Luo, 2014). Some *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains are non-pathogenic in animals (Fodah et al., 2014) and some strains only act as colonizers or commensals in humans (Martin et al., 2016). The accessory and core genomes both inhabit genes accountable for encoding traditional virulent factors such as capsule, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), siderophores, pili, fimbriae (S. Ali et al., 2022; A. H. Lee et al., 2021), as well as a new one a type VI secretion system, with the capsule as a main pathogenic factor utilized by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* that helps the pathogen to evade phagocytosis (Domenico, Salo, Cross, & Cunha, 1994).

- **1.2: Lipopolysaccharide (LPS)**

LPS also termed endotoxin- is a novel virulent factor, covering the outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria, inducing septic shock. Toll-like receptors (TL4) recognize LPS culminating in the initiation of the inflammatory cascade (Roger et al., 2009). It is considered as a part of core genome.

- **1.3: Structure of LPS**

Structural components of LPS include Lipid A, a core domain, and O antigen. Various O - serotypes are due to variability in the structure of O-antigen. Out of nine serotypes, only three i.e.O1-O3 are the main contributor to about 80% of infections by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Follador et al., 2016). The presence of O-antigen makes the isolate sensitive to the complement system while the absence makes it prone to be killed by the host's complement system. A variety of LPS makes the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* resistant to various antimicrobials including Polymyxin (Cheng et al., 2015).

Fig. 1.4: Schematic diagram of structure of bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS)

• 1.4: Siderophores

These are iron sequestering, low molecular weight molecules. Four types of siderophores are secreted by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Holden & Bachman, 2015) including enterobactin, salmochelin as well as a mixed type of siderophores having a higher affinity for iron than iron-chelating proteins found in host cells (Miethke & Marahiel, 2007). Enterobactin possesses a higher affinity than aerobactin which has the lowest affinity than all types of siderophores (Brock, Williams, Liceaga, & Wooldridge, 1991). Iron is a necessary component for the propagation as well as survival of bacteria during the disease development process (Bullen, Rogers, & Griffiths, 1972).

1.4.1: Enterobactin (Ent)-is a common type of siderophore encoded by the core genome of *klebsiella pneumoniae* (O'Brien & Gibson, 1970). Two clusters of genes such as entABCDEF and fepAABCDG present on chromosome 6t are involved in the synthesis as well as transport of enterobactin. Innate immune system can deprive bacteria of iron by binding 'ent' to its cells (K. D. Smith, 2007).

1.4.2: Salmochelin (Sal)- a part of the accessory genome, is a glucosylated derivative of enterobactin that protects bacteria from killing by the innate immune system (Hantke, Nicholson, Rabsch, & Winkelmann, 2003). Glucosylation is carried out by a gene cluster termed-iron named iron ABCDE which resides in chromosome or plasmid (Hsieh, Lin, Lee, Tsai, & Wang, 2008) and is mainly found in hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (hvKP) i.e.>90% cases (Bachman et al., 2011; El Fertas-Aissani, Messai, Alouache, & Bakour, 2013).

1.4.3: Mixed- type siderophores

Commonly secreted mixed type siderophores by *klebsiella pneumoniae* include yersinia bactin (Ybt) and aerobactin (Aer).

1.4.4: Yersiniabactin- was discovered in *Yersinia* species at first hence able to be called iron-uptake Island. Genes for the synthesis, transport as well as regulation of this siderophore are located on transposable chromosomal fragments that are 'high pathogenicity island'(Carniel, 2001). *Yersinia* bactin is mainly involved in respiratory tract infections and actively encourages pneumonia in murine models (Bachman et al., 2011). It is found in almost 75% of isolated *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

and was first found in *Yersinia*. About 90% of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. A cluster of *irb* gene encodes the protein for synthesis of *Yersinia* *bactin* (Hsieh et al., 2008). *Yersinia* *bactin* requires the other three siderophores as well for sequestering iron for survival and spread of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* such as in lung infection and the absence of the other three siderophores will render the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* restricted inside the lungs (Bachman et al., 2011).

1.4.5: Aerobactin- encoded by a plasmid, a major trigger and spreader of inflammation. Progression

from pneumonia to bacteremia is done by activation of host transcriptional regulatory protein named HIF-1 α via iron chelation (Holden, Breen, Houle, Dozois, & Bachman, 2016). Ton B is a protein encoded by a gene located on the chromosome, acts as a virulence factor in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and controls the siderophore functions by regulating the movement of iron across the bacterial cell membrane (Hsieh et al., 2008).

Schematic diagram of virulence factors of Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

1.5: Pili-are filamentous structures, about 10 μ m in length and 1-11 nm in diameter (Ofek, Doyle, Ofek, & Doyle, 1994). There are two types of pili on *Klebsiella pneumoniae* which include type 1 and type 3. Type-1 pili aids in pathogenesis via adherence to mucosal or epithelial surfaces in humans whereas, type- 3 is mainly involved in biofilm formation (Schroll et al., 2010). Both of these pili are part of the core genome (Andrade, de Veiga Ramos, Marin, Fonseca, & Vicente, 2014; Lery et al., 2014).

1.6: Efflux pumps

Efflux pumps are the other major contributor in inducing antibiotic resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* by excreting antibiotics from bacterial cells (Filgona, Banerjee, & Anupurba, 2015) or

by resisting antimicrobial peptides formed by the innate immune system (Pamp, Gjermansen, Johansen, & Tolker-Nielsen, 2008).

1.7: Type VI Secretion system

Type VI secretion system (T6SS) was discovered in *Vibrio cholera*, and has a syringe-like apparatus that harbors the cell membrane of bacterial cells, aiding in the delivery of substances such as proteins, effector molecules, and toxins in bacterial cells (Journet & Cascales, 2016; Taylor, van Raaij, & Leiman, 2018; J. Wang, Brodmann, & Basler, 2019). This secretion system is substantially found in gram-negative whose function is to counteract bacterial cells or to transport host-damaging substrates to eukaryotes and prokaryotes (Han et al., 2019), thus helps to

compete with other bacterial species (Hood et al., 2010). It is also involved in the uptake of metal ions such as iron, manganese, and zinc (Lin et al., 2017; Si et al., 2017). Three T6SS clusters have been discovered in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* named H1-T6SS, H2-T6SS, and H3-T6SS with H1-T6SS is widely studied and has anti-bacterial activity (Hood et al., 2010). These proteins are mainly toxins in nature thus, function to remove prey cells from bacteria or by modifying the function of eukaryotic cells (Cianfanelli, Monlezun, & Coulthurst, 2016; Hachani, Wood, & Filloux, 2016). But some of these proteins delivered by the T6SS system are not toxins but may be metal chelators (Han et al., 2019). Heterogeneity of effectors is achieved through horizontal gene transfer, gene duplication as well and recombination via conserved regions, thus, positioning new toxins at a specific area in the genome (Salomon, 2016; Unterweger et al., 2015). The type VI system is encoded by a cluster of T6SS genes containing 1-3 loci per strain (Journet & Cascales, 2016). This secretory system is present in accessory as well as the core genome, thus regulating competition with other bacteria for survival and also taking part in pathogenesis. Various recent studies have identified T6SS effectors in *klebsiella pneumoniae* (Journet & Cascales, 2016).

1.8: Beta lactamase producing *klebsiella pneumoniae*

Beta lactamases are the enzymes produced mainly by gram-negative bacilli, conferring resistance to beta-lactams by decomposition of beta-lactam ring present in antibiotics by binding to carbonyl moiety of beta-lactam ring with leads to hydrolysis of amide bond (Fisher, Meroueh, & Mobashery, 2005). It is a primary mechanism of natural or acquired resistance. In *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, resistance to beta-lactams is inborn, as the core genome is involved in forming these enzymes. SHV is the only type of beta-lactamase, encoded by genes in chromosomes, and is responsible for ampicillin resistance (Bialek-Davenet et al., 2014). Selective environmental pressure gave rise to beta-lactamases from penicillin-binding protein

(Meroueh, Minasov, Lee, Shoichet, & Mobashery, 2003).

1.8.1: Classification of Beta-Lactamases

There are four classes of beta-lactamases ranging from A to D on the basis of amino acid sequence (Bush, 2013a). The class-A beta-lactamases named serine beta-lactamases as they contain one or two zinc ions at the active site hence named metallo-lactamases (MBLs) are the principal beta-lactamases that are novel resistant tools mainly in gram-negative bacilli but less frequently in gram-positive bacteria (Bonomo, 2017; Bush, 2013b). There are more than 2000 class A enzymes that have been identified such as TEM, CTX-MKPC, or CARBA. The majority of beta-lactamases are encoded by chromosome e.g. CfxA type, CepA, and CME. These enzymes hydrolyze especially cephalosporins but also penicillins and aztreonam (Bush, 2013a).

1.8.2: New Delhi metallo-beta lactamase (NDMBL)

New Delhi metallo-beta lactamase (NDMBL) is a type of beta-lactamase that hydrolyzes beta-lactams and carbapenems excluding monobactams. NDM-1 is the most recently discovered class of NDMBL, which was first uncovered from *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated in Sweden in 2008 from an Indian. NDM is a monomeric, metalloenzyme that breakdowns all beta-lactams except aztreonam (Kumarasamy et al., 2010). Infections due to NDM-1-positive strains have high mortality rates. NDM-1 is prevalent worldwide, indicating a challenge for clinical management as well as public health (Dortet, Poirel, & Nordmann, 2014).

1.8.2.1: Subtypes of MBLs

There are three subtypes of MBLs such as B1, B2, and B3 based on amino acid sequence identity. Type B1 and B3 have 2 zinc ions that enable them to attack multiple antibiotics including penicillins, cephalosporins, and carbapenems (Bush, 2013a; Frere, Galleni, Bush, & Dideberg, 2005). On the other hand, type B2 has only one zinc ion, thus enabling it to resist carbapenems only (Bush & Jacoby, 2010; Palzkill, 2013). The majority of

identified MBLs are from subclass B1 (F Mojica, A Bonomo, & Fast, 2016).

1.8.2.2: Limited Spectrum beta-lactamases (LSBLs)

This group includes beta-lactamases belonging to 2b and 2c as per functional classification. ACI-1 ESBL beta-lactamases identified in many species originated from the gut flora of animals and humans by the acquisition of aci 1 gene via transposon (Rands et al., 2018). The plasmid-encoded beta-lactamase enzyme -BKC-1 which is a weak carbapenemase, is the only plasmid-encoded enzyme that has been reported in Brazil, in two strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* that also produces Extended -spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL), but it is a weak carbapenemase (Naas, Dortet, & I Iorga, 2016).

- **1.9: Molecular nature of group B, C and E**

The enzymes of group B are ESBLs in their phenotype. This groups possesses many residues in which C69 and C238 are conserved ones that affect shape of active site via forming disulfide bridge (Naas et al., 2016; C. A. Smith et al., 2016). Group C contain natural ESBLs encoded by genes of chromosomal, plamid origin and also by transposable elements. Here classification is functional type, based upon penicillinase activity (Bonnet, 2004; Naas et al., 2016).

- **2.0: Carbapenemases-The Carba Cluster**

Carbapenemases (KPC,NDM, OXA-48 and VIM) producing Enterobacteriaceae confer major threat to human being and their genes spread via plasmids free genetic elements, loss of porins and overexpression of efflux systems (Benulič et al., 2020; Pitout, Nordmann, & Poirel, 2015). Italy is an endemic country for carbapenemases (Grundmann et al., 2017). Two genes named as *bla*OXA-48-like has been obtained in 53.1% and *bla*NDM-1 has been obtained in 15.6% with 21.9% isolates exhibited both genes. *bla*KPC-2 and *bla*VIM-1 gene (Benulič et al., 2020). This group includes potent carbapenemases belonging to functional class 2f, mostly derived from Enterobacteriaceae, except VCC-1 which is

derived from *Vibrio cholera* (Hammerl et al., 2017; Mangat et al., 2016). Some of these are derived from chromosomes such as BIC, IMI-1 NmcA, NME, etc while others such as KPC and FRI are of plasmid origin (Naas et al., 2016).

2.1: Mechanism of action of Carbapenemases

Carbapenem resistance in addition to carbapenemases in gram-negative rods may be due to the activation of beta-lactamases, the presence of efflux pumps, or their increased activity (Pfeifer, Cullik, & Witte, 2010), loss or alterations of porins as well as due to modifications in penicillin-binding proteins (PBP) (Gilbert & McBain, 2003).

2.2: Classification of Carbapenemases

Most common carbapenemases in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* include class -A, class- B, and class- D beta-lactamases that their ubiquity varies topographically (C.-R. Lee et al., 2016; van Duin & Doi, 2017). Class -Carbapenemases, named *Klebsiella pneumoniae* carbapenemase (KPC) is the main enzyme but the commonest class is the class -B beta-lactamases having worldwide distribution (Kilic & Baysallar, 2015; Mezzatesta et al., 2011).

2.3: Capsule

Capsule is the most novel and well-studied virulence factor in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The cps gene cluster on the chromosome is present in Carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (C-KP) as well as hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (hv-KP) (Whitney & Howell, 2013). In *Klebsiella pneumoniae* about 78 capsular types have been found out. Capsular specific antigens of smooth as well as rough colonies both, react with anti-sera (Ko et al., 2002). Capsular polysaccharide protects from a variety of environmental agents of a physical, chemical, or biochemical nature (Whitfield, Wear, & Sande, 2020). Capsule has been used previously for designing of vaccine but there is no licensed vaccine or therapy yet that can be implemented clinically (Opoku-Temeng et al., 2019). There is a dire need to develop vaccine by targeting capsular antigens, in order to prevent

infections resulting from *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, which is a globally spread, lethal bug.

2.4: Targets of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* other than Beta Lactamases

Besides Beta-lactamases, enzymes involved in metabolic processes can also be targeted to prevent infections caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* FabB, FabH, and FabI. FabI is important for antibiotic development (Regueiro et al., 2011).

2.5: Structure, classification of integrons, their Sources and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) spread

Integrons are freely moving genetic elements that capture exogenous genes. They are primitive elements, involved in causing genetic complexity which in turn leads to phenotypic variation thus helping in adaptations (Gillings, 2014). Researchers have reported animal meat as a major source of transmission of resistant genes to human beings (He et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2019), with pig- the main source of class-1 and class- 2 -integrons (Marchant & Moreno, 2013).

2.5.1: Classification of integrons

Generally speaking, the integrons are classified by two genes such as *intI* and *attI*, with *attI* being the most important from a classification point of view (S. Zhang et al., 2020). There are three main core features in all integrons with the main function of picking up external genomes and expressing them as a part of gene cassettes (Boucher, Labbate, Koenig, & Stokes, 2007). The first core is-*intI* gene encodes an enzyme named as -integron integrase, which belongs to the tyrosine recombinase family, catalyzing reintegration between new gene cassettes (GCs) (Messier & Roy, 2001). The second core property is *attI* -which is an integron-related recombination site. The third one is the integron-linked promoter that aids in the expression of gene-cassette complex (Partridge et al., 2000). On the basis of *intI*, there are many classes of integrons with class-1, class-2 and class-3 *intI* are of most significance (S. Zhang et al., 2020). Integrons are novel antibiotic resistant inducers and act via possession, expression as well distribution of resistant genes (Gillings, 2014). The mechanism of spreading antimicrobial

resistance (AMR) varies from class to class which is credited to the type of GCs grabbed by a specific integron (Gillings, 2014).

2.6: Plasmids found in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*
IncF-This type of plasmid is found in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is important for spreading a gene - *blaSHV-2* from clinically isolated *Escherichia coli* as well as from animals which the sources of food in France (IncFIB, IncFII, IncFII-FIB), specific *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains isolated from China (IncFIB), Portugal (IncFII) (Pouget, Coutinho, Reid-Smith, & Boerlin, 2013; Rodrigues, Machado, Ramos, Peixe, & Novais, 2014). IncFII plasmid has also been observed in clinically isolated *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Serratia marcescens* encoding *blaSHV-5* gene (Zienkiewicz, Kern-Zdanowicz, Carattoli, Gniadkowski, & Cegłowski, 2013).

IncHI2-This plasmid is involved in the dissemination of gene-*blaSHV-12* (Mnif et al., 2013) in different bacterial species including *Escherichia coli*, *klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Enterobacter cloacae* in humans from different countries (Chen et al., 2015; Rodrigues et al., 2014). Some plasmids of this class also encode other resistance genes such as SHV ESBLs (Chen et al., 2015).

IncI1-This is a class of plasmid that carries *blaSHV-2*, *blaSHV-2a*, and *blaSHV-12* with *blaSHV-2* and *12* are retrieved from human infections (Chen et al., 2015; Markovska, Schneider, Ivanova, Mitov, & Bauernfeind, 2014).

IncX3-This includes plasmid that spread the *blaSHV-12* gene. These conjugative plasmids occur in different bacterial species e.g. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella enterica*, and *Serratia marcescens*, and also vary geographically (Dobiasova & Dolejska, 2016; Feng et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2016).

2.7: Spread of ARGs in agriculture, animals and birds

Worldwide excessive usage and excretion of antibiotics is lethally involved in increasing drug resistance (S. Zhang et al., 2020). In addition, the transfer of resistant genes via integrons, plasmids

as well transposons, within and between bacterial species also enhances spread of antimicrobial resistance (Fuentes-Castillo et al., 2019). Antimicrobial resistant genes with class -1 integrons are primarily present in agricultural products, raw meat, aquatic food, swine manure (Xiong, Sun, Shi, & Yan, 2019) and mastitic milk (T. Ali et al., 2016) while sources of genes with class 2 and 3 integrons include fruits and vegetables (Jones-Dias et al., 2016), with oro-fecal route involved in transmission in ExPEC reported from Algeria (Messaili, Messai, & Bakour, 2019). Class-2 integrons are also found by researchers in feces of humans (Silva, Carvalho, Igrejas, & Poeta, 2017), pets and wild animals (Alonso, González-Barrio, Tenorio, Ruiz-Fons, & Torres, 2016), livestock and poultry (Tewari et al., 2019). Integrons should be reported to reduce multidrug resistance and also for monitoring purpose (S. Zhang et al., 2020). A study carried out in Tunisia has shown the wild birds as a source of class -1 integrons with absent genetic cassettes (Ben Yahia et al., 2018) and owls are the main contributor to spread ARGs (Fuentes-Castillo et al., 2019). Therefore, monitoring and surveillance of spreading antimicrobial resistant genes worldwide is a crucial and urgent matter (S. Zhang et al., 2020).

2.7.1: Mode of transmission of ARGs

Plasmid is the main location as well as mode of transmission of ARGs in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Navon-Venezia et al., 2017) hence it is involved in carrying drug-resistant genes from environment to pathogenic bacteria isolated from clinical samples (Wyres & Holt, 2018). Soil is the main source of gene transfer (Popa, Hazkani-Covo, Landan, Martin, & Dagan, 2011) in Enterobacteriaceae via plasmid, which mainly resides in soil (Klümper et al., 2015). There are three plasmids in a genome of single *Klebsiella pneumoniae* than other species e.g. ST11, strain carried six plasmids out of which three plasmids carry resistance genes, out of which is a source of carbapenamase (Liu et al., 2012). Hygiene practice should be primarily followed to solve this problem (Moghadam et al., 2021).

2.8: Colistin resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*
Mutations in the gene named *crrB* result in CrrC leading to increased resistance (Cheng, Lin, Lin, & Wang, 2016; Pitt et al., 2019) as well as efflux pump in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* -AcrAB, which is a major mechanism of drug resistance. (Padilla et al., 2010). This efflux pump encoded by *acrRAB* (De Clercq, Eckstein, Sternbach, & Merigan, 1982) is also involved in inducing pneumonia by counteracting the innate immune system (Padilla et al., 2010). MgrB is a transmembrane protein that is very small in size, produced by the activation of a system named PhoPQ (Poirel et al., 2015).

In addition, *mgrB* and *mcr-1* genes induce resistance via changing lipopolysaccharide (LPS). One study has shown that strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* that are deficient in *mgr-1* gene, possess other genes such as *mgrB* and *phoQ*, while in strains that are *mgr-1* positive, mutations in *crrA* and *pmrB* genes are mutated (Zhu et al., 2021). In contrast, a study done by (H. Zhang et al., 2018) has shown that *mgr-1* gene has no role in inducing colistin resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from clinical samples in whom an inactive form of *mgrB* gene is present. Thus, *mgrB* gene makes *Klebsiella pneumoniae* resistant to colistin by stabilizing the membrane structure of bacteria as well as by inducing alteration on lipid-A which in turn leads to less affinity of the drug for pathogen (Yap, Cheng, Chang, Lim, & Lai, 2022). Other researchers named. (Olaitan, Morand, & Rolain, 2014) .has concluded similarly to (Yap et al., 2022) that *mgrB* gene is the main assistant that favours resistance development in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Poirel et al., 2015).

Materials and Methodology

Data was collected from various databases named Google scholar, Pubmed Central, Science Direct, Wiley online library. A total of 140 articles from 2016-2023 were downloaded. Relevant data was extracted after critical reading. Irrelevant articles were discarded.

Conclusion

Klebsiella pneumoniae is an emerging pathogen worldwide causing numerous life-threatening diseases especially, hospitalized patients. The

discovered antimicrobials were effective previously but due to genetic as well as geographical variations in genes harboring plasmids or chromosomes, the available antimicrobials have become less effective. Therefore, the treatment against this pandrug-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* has become a great concern over the globe.

This pathogen possesses a variety of virulence factors including capsule, fimbriae, pili, siderophores, and type VI secretion system, the genes of which reside in plasmids or chromosomes. These genes can be transferred within or between species or between the same or different species. There are various sources of acquiring resistant genes including agricultural waste, fruits or vegetables contaminated with human or animal feces containing excessive amounts of excreted antimicrobials, sewage, mastitic milk, wild animals, and birds. Capsules and siderophores in hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are the best targets for developing vaccines and medications. Designing new diagnostic methods is challenging.

Future suggestions

Inappropriate usage of antimicrobials by humans, with or without prescription for themselves or for their animals needed to be diminished. Proper hygiene conditions and, control of aquatic, agricultural as well as wild environments is a prime concern. As the geographical distribution of plasmid encoding genes and nonplasmid encoded virulent genes is different, whole genome sequencing of isolated *K. pneumoniae* should be done at a large scale worldwide to design a new and complex vaccine as well as specimen-specific antibiotics for this pathogen, be given worldwide. In addition, designing of siderophore receptor inhibitors and hence disrupting the organism's metabolism will also be a key threat to the organism's survival. Recent studies report the alarming convergence of hypervirulence and carbapenem resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, producing CR-hvKP strains with high mortality rates. Whole-genome sequencing, AI-based surveillance, and multi-omics approaches are improving detection and prediction of

antimicrobial resistance. Novel therapeutic strategies such as capsule-based conjugate vaccines, siderophore receptor inhibitors, bacteriophage therapy, and CRISPR-Cas-based antimicrobials are emerging as promising future interventions.

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